

DIFFICULTIES POSSIBILITIES AND POTENTIAL ORGANIZATIONAL IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT I LIGHT OF COVID- 19 ISSUES

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Abstract

Many organizations were forced to quickly transition to remote work in response to the pandemic. This has created a number of challenges for HR managers, such as ensuring that employees have the necessary equipment and software, providing support for employees who are struggling with remote work, and maintaining a sense of company culture. Due to COVID-19, Human Resource Management (HRM) experts operate in a complex and challenging environment. This study is an overview of the relevant literature investigating how COVID-19 has affected human resource management, intending to expand the field of management studies. It details the most pressing problems and promising prospects of the new pandemic. There are two primary types of variables in the framework (independent and dependent). Where Covid-19 issues will be an independent variable, health risks at the workplace, employee performance, and change in management of an organization are all dependent variables, and Human Resource Management (HRM) practices will play the role of moderator between dependent and independent variables. This study reviews the research on the effects of COVID-19 on Human Resource Management (HRM), and its primary goal is to provide useful information to the reader. Very little research has examined this effect, but in this research, secondary data sources such as library resources and web-based journal material were used since they were relevant to the target of the work. The COVID-19 pandemic has created a number of challenges for HR Management, the sudden shift to remote work has created a number of challenges for HR Management, such as ensuring that employees have the necessary equipment and software, providing support for employees who are struggling with remote work, and maintaining a sense of company culture, the pandemic has disrupted the traditional hiring process, making it more difficult to find and on board new employees. There needs to be more research on the effects of this crisis on Human Resource Management (HRM). They must devise novel strategies to ensure their companies' continued viability and assist their individuals in dealing with this unusual state. It provides managers and HRM professionals with advice on how to best take advantage of the chances presented by these problems. Moreover, HR managers need to ensure that employees are safe and healthy during the pandemic. This includes providing personal protective equipment, implementing social distancing measures, and offering mental health support. The study's It offers extraordinary visions of how to ease these difficulties or deal with the effects on the general workforce. The overarching impartial studies provide a basic outline to direct upcoming studies on the COVID-19 difficulties in the workplace.

Keywords: Human Resource Management (HRM) Issues in Covid-19, Changes in Organization Management, Health Risks on Workplace, Employee Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this study, the global community has been reeled by the extraordinary health calamity, and we are talking about COVID-19. Wide-ranging repercussions on economies, societies, people, and enterprises have been seen worldwide. It is predicted that a coronavirus-caused acute respiratory crisis outbreak will begin in December 2019, which was initially reported in Wuhan, China (Hamouche, 2021). The virus quickly spread, and on March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization declared the outbreak a worldwide pandemic. In response to the fast spread of the COVID-19 virus, these nations have undertaken several non-pharmaceutical measures, such as increased social isolation, to slow the virus's progress (Vahdat, 2021). People have been quarantined; schools, universities, and non-essential companies and NGOs have closed temporarily; travel has been limited; flights have been cancelled, and large-scale public gatherings and social activities have been banned (Alghizzawi et al. 2023; Alhumaid, Habes, and Salloum 2021; Almesafri and Habes 2023). When taken together, these measures, plus the global slowdown caused by the COVID-19 epidemic, contributed to a rise in the unemployment rate in several nations. Current unemployed totals are all over the map, from a million in the U.S. to 1.76 million in Japan (Przytuła et al., 2020). As a result of COVID-19, there is a real possibility that within a short time frame, half of the working population may be unable to do their jobs (Carnevale & Hatak, 2020). Management of a company's or organization's human resources in such a way that they contribute to the company's or organization's competitive advantage is the goal of human resource management. Its goal is to boost organizational productivity to achieve its strategic goals better. Management of Human Resource (HR) is an organizational strategy focused on people issues such as employee development, benefits, and workplace culture (Alsuwaidi 2023; Al Dulaimi and Al Hindawy 2023). Employment and benefits administration, training and development, employee relations, and pay and benefits are only some of its many duties (Carnevale & Hatak, 2020).

Businesses have attempted reopening amid the continuing epidemic to recoup from the economic blow they have suffered, but with new restrictions and ways of operating (such as physical separation between employees) that have yet to be eliminated (Vahdat, 2021). Consequently, this epidemic has created a complicated and hard environment for managers and management (HRM) practitioners, who have had to devise inventive ways to keep their firms running and assist their staff in dealing with the demands of this unprecedented circumstance (Przytuła et al., 2020). There is very little research on the influence of COVID-19 on Human Resource Management (HRM), its obstacles, and prospects for Human Resource Management (HRM) in organizations. However, managers and Human Resource Management (HRM) experts need relevant information to get them through this crisis efficiently and effectively, support staffers, and maintain their company's business (Vahdat, 2021). In reality, most industries absence the incomes necessary to effectively respond to crises when they arise. Hence the significance of the scientific community's role in assisting organizations by supplying knowledge pertinent to this new epidemic. Accordingly, this research aims to analyze COVID-19's effects on human resource management, illuminating the most serious issues and promising future directions in the sector. Due to the paucity of previous works, this project aims to broaden the scope of management studies (Przytuła et al., 2020). To lessen the

pandemic's effect on productivity, Human Resource (HR) managers during the covid-19 period prioritized health and safety at work (for both workers and employers) and the extensive use of telework. Human Resource (HR) experts have been preparing their teams to face the outbreak by encouraging them to strengthen their flexibility and productivity. The world's newest pandemic, the coronavirus, has presented Human Resource (HR) professionals with several new issues (Vahdat, 2021). The recent incident of the coronavirus virus has merely added to the many difficulties in the area of Human Resources (HR). Because of the Corona Virus, Human Resource (HR) professionals have new concerns, such as how to ensure employees stay healthy, clean, and mentally prepared to do their jobs despite the restrictions imposed by the virus (Przytuła et al., 2020). While many firms were forced to reduce hours and hours of operation, those in the food and drug sectors, for example, could not. Because of this, companies that could not manage to close down began allowing employees to work remotely. As the lockdown is lifted and businesses reopen; however, the governmental and private sectors face unprecedented difficulties, particularly with the enormous workload that has accumulated since the start of the covid-19 epidemic (Vahdat, 2021).

2. BACKGROUND STUDY

Human Resource Management (HRM) was first renamed personnel management in the 1980s because of the work of famous economist Michael Porter, who found that workers were the key to any company's success. This rebranding was required due to the ongoing economic crisis, rapid industrialization, and technological advances (Przytuła et al., 2020). Because of their growing importance to the company's performance, Human Resource Management (HRM) has replaced personnel management. Human Resource (HR) used to be responsible for helping the whole company, but in recent years, companies have begun to recognize that their people are their greatest asset. Human Resource Management (HRM) includes strategic planning, while personnel management is limited to hiring new employees, placing existing employees in appropriate positions, and ensuring legal compliance. Organizational competitiveness and productivity have benefited from the shift from people management to Human Resource Management (HRM). It has been noted that increasing productivity inside an organization is a primary goal for the human resources department (Kutieshat et al., 2022).

As a result, public and private businesses are now understood to be made up of people working together toward a common purpose. Therefore, Human Resource Management (HRM) has become a popular area of study in the late 20th century. Human Resource Management (HRM), or Human Resource Management (HRM), oversees and enhances an organization's Human Resource (HR) (Przytuła et al., 2020). As stated before, this is because efficacy is the yardstick by which the success of an organization's aims may be judged. In this context, Human Resource (HR) managers' duties would include setting an example of how Human Resource (HR) growth may contribute to attaining business goals. Human Resource Management (HRM) is a set of practices and strategies for effectively supervising and leading an organization's people at all levels to accomplish its goals (Wissemann et al., 2022).

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The study's primary goal was to identify the difficulties Human Resource (HR) managers encountered in maintaining the Human Resource (HR) expertise in their organizations throughout the covid-19 pandemic. It offers extraordinary visions of how to ease these difficulties or deal with the effects on the general workforce. The overarching impartial studies provide a basic outline to direct upcoming studies on the COVID-19 difficulties in the workplace, in addition to analysing and using past research to unravel the dilemma (Kutieshat et al., 2022).

4. SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

Researchers and businesses may use the findings of this study to plan for the future and take effective actions to lessen the influence of the coronavirus on their operations. In addition, this study's discussion of current difficulties provides a literature overview of pertinent COVID-19-related Human Resource (HR) challenges for academics and professionals (Kutieshat et al., 2022). The research is broken down into four parts: background information; elaboration on key concepts; a review of relevant literature; and a discussion of potential approaches to resolving the issues raised (Kutieshat et al., 2022).

5. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

There are two primary types of variables in the framework (independent and dependent). Where Covid-19 issues will be an independent variable, health risks at the workplace, employee performance, and change in management of an organization are all dependent variables, and Human Resource Management (HRM) practices will play the role of moderator between dependent and independent variables. These are shown in figure no 2 below:

6. METHODOLOGY

This study reviews the research on the effects of COVID-19 on Human Resource Management (HRM), and its primary goal is to provide useful information to the reader (Ali et al. 2021; Habes, Ali, Khalid, et al. 2021; Salloum et al. 2021). Very little research has examined this effect, but in this research, secondary data sources such as library resources and web-based

journal material were used since they were relevant to the target of the work. Accordingly, I began a search for publications that first evaluated the broad connection between COVID-19 and Human Resource Management (HRM) and then for studies that analysed the influence of this pandemic on each Human Resource (HR) function and practice, such as staffing (recruitment) and remuneration (Kyeremateng, 2021). We used a mix of phrases relating to coronavirus or COVID-19; Human Resource (HR) administration; Human Resource Management (HRM); pandemic, and Human Resource Management (HRM) responsibilities to search for publications in Google Scholar and Semantic Scholar (e.g., compensation and staffing). Manual searches for articles were conducted (Aoun, Lagadec, and Habes 2022; Habes, Ali, and Pasha 2021; Wang, Ibrahim, and Li 2022). We looked for pieces that will appear between Dec 2019 and Feb 2022. Publications focusing on epidemiology have yet to be considered. All of the studied papers are provided in the paper's References section (Koirala et al., 2020).

7. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Coronavirus Pandemic

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), a recently found virus called covid-19 is to blame for the coronavirus pandemic. The virus is often spread by a person's saliva or nasal discharge. Because of its high transmission rate, Covid-19 has been labeled a pandemic. At first, in December 2019, scientists thought the coronavirus first appeared in a Wuhan, China, food market serving the surrounding Hubei region. At this time, we do not know where the infection first appeared. The spread of the COVID-19 epidemic has hampered several businesses' operations. The Human Resource (HR) department now faces a significant obstacle because of this. To combat the spread of this infection, several businesses have used new methods of communication, such as email and conferencing, instead of traditional in-person meetings (Wissemann et al., 2022). As businesses begin to reopen, Human Resource (HR) experts must fill vacancies in the medical staff to avoid the growth of covid-19 and ensure compliance with the tight isolation centre policy.

Human Resource (HR) professionals also have challenges in protecting the safety and wellness of their workforce in the face of the epidemic. The stress on the remaining staff is compounded by the fact that Human Resource (HR) experts now must deal with a flood of paperwork caused by the increased frequency with which employees are being laid off. Managers in Human Resource (HR) would also be tasked with assuring the affected individuals that they would be okay despite the millions of layoffs that will occur (Wissemann et al., 2022). Personnel directors should support remote employees to maintain office relationships even when they are physically apart. The global effect of the coronavirus as of December 20, 2020 (Przytuła et al., 2020). For this investigation, many databases were consulted to compile the necessary information. Database use data is shown in Figure 1 below:

2. Limited Number of Staff Working On-Site

Telecommuting has become more common since the amount of labour required has grown due to the absence of employees caused by the coronavirus. Those still in the office must deal with more work since more people cannot come in due to illness. Therefore, more people are working from home. Covid-19-related situations have also led to a significant drop in attendance, particularly among personnel in key roles. Personnel managers, whose job is to make the most of their staff's abilities, face considerable uncertainty due to these problems (Przytuła et al., 2020). To address this issue, management may institute measures that incentivize personnel already present to stay late at the office to get more done and make up for absent co-workers. Additionally, the cap on overtime might be raised to compensate for lost time. Similarly, to safeguard traditional office hours, overtime pay may be instituted, but only for telework (Wissemann et al., 2022).

3. Covid-19 Health Risks Within the Workplace

It has been shown that the workplace poses a significant danger to the rapid spread of Covid-19. Companies employ highly trained specialists and those with lower levels of education, many of whom come from outlying areas. Workers in these industries often play a significant role in the furtherance of the epidemic. Public spaces, including restrooms, locker rooms, cafeterias, hallways, exits, elevators, and other high-traffic zones, are prime locations for transmitting diseases like the coronavirus (Wissemann et al., 2022). Therefore, for continuity and productivity, businesses must provide their employees with a safe and healthy workplace that prioritizes their mental and physical well-being. Acquiring necessary human, monetary, and material means, such as doing a risk assessment and determining how to prioritize needs, creating a detailed building plan, and contacting health and workforce experts as required, should all be part of a strategy for containing the virus. Human Resource (HR) managers should respond by taking reasonable precautions to prevent workers and consumers from catching the coronavirus (Wissemann et al., 2022). The Health and Safety Department did a risk assessment and found the following steps would reduce the spread of the coronavirus:

- Continue to follow the advice of health professionals on cleaning, hygiene, and hand cleanliness to ensure employee and patient safety.
- Emails, videos, flyers, and public announcements should all be used to spread information about preventative actions.
- Maintain canteen sanitation and safety standards. Cameras may be set up to watch and supervise certain areas to check on individuals to see whether they are following the rules.
- Organizations should check in with afflicted employees frequently via emails, phone calls, and meetings to mitigate risks to their physical and mental health caused by isolation or coronavirus worry. Managers should also have frequent conversations with their staff on the issue of weariness, stressing the need to take regular breaks and leaves and limiting workers' total time on the job.

- Restrict or forbid any needless business trips and instruct workers to spend time alone after returning from any trip.

4. Challenges and Opportunities for Human Resource Management (HRM) in the Era of Covid 19

Human Resource Management (HRM) refers to the study and practice of improving organizational performance by carefully managing their most valuable asset: their employees. COVID-19 has profoundly affected it, posing serious difficulties for management and Human Resource Management (HRM) professionals (Kyeremateng, 2021). In this section, we look at this impact and these challenges in the study of strategic Human Resource Management (HRM) and workplace situations, as well as Human Resource Management (HRM) operations, including staffing, performance assessment, training & development, pay administration, health and safety management, and worker interactions. However, while being treated separately, these Human Resource Management (HRM) duties all depend on one another. That is why it is important to consider how a change in one Human Resource Management (HRM) function can affect another (Mansour, & Nogues, 2022).

5. Covid-19 and Strategic Human Resource Management (HRM)

Strategic Human Resource Management (HRM) involves the vertical alignment of Human Resource Management (HRM) with the business's overall strategy and the horizontal cohesion of Human Resource Managements (HRM) many sub-functions. Human resource management's primary objective is to put workers to work, meeting the business's strategic goals. Strategic agility is necessary to guarantee that the organization's objectives are met, whatever the circumstances (Mansour, & Nogues, 2022). In order to be successful, businesses must be able to correctly plan and allocate resources, coordinate the necessary mechanisms, and effectively use their expertise and data. The originality and complexity of COVID-19 provide a substantial barrier that might jeopardize the organization's ability to achieve its objectives. Organizational members are often instructed to use a "normal times" lens to economic data, as prescribed by most conventional models.

Consequently, forecasting 'abnormal times' is difficult. Because of this, it is possible that predicting the company's business, such as resource allocation and preparedness, is challenging (Mansour, & Nogues, 2022). The true reason for the uncertainty is because of COVID-19. Some researchers are already projecting a widespread outbreak of COVID-19, but many economists anticipate the consequences of this disease will linger for at least another year, until 2021. Several vaccines have been developed in recent years. However, it is still uncertain when this virus will die out, not whether its impacts on organizational patterns will be temporary or permanent (Kyeremateng, 2021). As a result, Strategic planning may take much work, especially for newly-minted executives and Human Resource Management (HRM) experts. Although most businesses could not give their workers sufficient information about their management plan or expected responses to the epidemic, doing so would have helped decrease stress and enhance confidence and motivation among workers (Kyeremateng, 2021). A substantial correlation between staff retention and access to pandemic-related updates and

information was found in the research. However, it may be challenging if businesses cannot get this data, particularly if they are in an unreceptive and existing style owing to the unprecedented nature of this epidemic. Post-COVID, post-SARS age, building organizational resilience is essential to a company's long-term success in COVID-19. In reality, businesses need to come up with creative procedures to absorb and confront the disturbance that impends their being in the face of the doubt brought on by this widespread (Mansour, & Nogues, 2022).

6. Working Condition in Covid-19

It has remained thought that "the heart of paid labour and employment relationships" is the employed setting. They address a wide variety of workplace concerns, including but not limited to: focus on the task (times of work, time out breaks, and work agendas), recompense, and the job's physical problems and mental stresses. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, several businesses have had to change their working environments significantly. Most businesses now require workers to do some or all of their duties from home (Kyeremateng, 2021). For instance, Twitter allows its staff to work remotely forever, while Google has declared that its employees will do so until at least the Summer of 2021. However, remote workers only account for a tiny percentage of the total workforce. This is because manufacturing sectors are not a good fit for remote work, and not all jobs can be performed from home. There were two alternatives for companies whose activities prevented them from giving such working conditions to their workers (Kyeremateng, 2021).

Organizations may enable laborers to be physically present while adhering to safety precautions like keeping a safe distance and wearing protective gear, or they can let them go. The research found that employees whose occupations need them to be physically present are at a higher risk of being let go. Managers of Human Resource (HR) must decide which positions may remain to be performed remotely, which must stay inside the office, and which must be terminated as a consequence of the epidemic (Hart & Halden, 2020). Therefore, managers and Human Resource Management (HRM) experts confront significant challenges due to these unexpected and extreme organizational transformations. They may also affect how workers feel about their mental health, how well they fit in with their workplace, and how they interact with their co-workers and superiors. With the establishment of work schedules for various groups of workers, physical presence in the workplace has been preserved with stringent protection measures (such as physical separation and wearing protective masks). The main difficulty here is ensuring that these safeguards are followed, and in doing so, schedules are planned for employees that take their personal lives into mind (Kyeremateng, 2021).

Managers and Human Resource Management (HRM) specialists needed help in implementing remote work. As a first step, check that distant employees are admitted to all of the necessary equipment to do their work effectively. In reality, remote work necessitates using expensive software like Zoom, Windows remote desktops, team viewer, and Windows team to allow communication between workers and management (Hart & Halden, 2020). Second, to realign the remuneration of remote workers with their actual time and effort put in. Additionally, Human resources specialists should assist managers just starting with leading distributed teams. The lack of face-to-face contact, the inability to rely on colleagues for guidance, and the

absence of one-on-one discussions are all factors that Human Resource (HR) professionals must consider when planning for remote workers' potential isolation and the resulting negative mental health effects. Considering the potential for family interruptions and the need to juggle various jobs while working from home, it may also be mentally taxing for these workers.

Furthermore, the rising usage of ICT might provide an eternal sense of urgency, perhaps leading to expectations regarding workers' permanent accessibility. Because of their increased reliance on email, workers' workloads may grow when they can do so from home. Some writers note an increase in remote workers' cases of "technostress," or stress caused by technological innovations (Kyeremateng, 2021).

In particular, if workers use email as their exclusive means of interaction, this might negatively impact their mental health. Human Resource Management (HRM) experts have introduced virtual social possibilities, like online lunches and coffee breaks, as one of many efforts to aid their workers (Aday, 2020). Time away from the office and co-workers help employees get through the crisis. However, they also offer a severe dilemma for organizations since, in addition to being adopted in the middle of unexpected changes, these processes are foreign to employees and managers who have not been taught or psychologically prepared for such advances, which could increase their perceptions of person-environment misfit and discontent if they miss the personal interactions, they were accustomed to before the pandemic outbreak. Additionally, it is possible that workers' ability to learn the tacit knowledge associated with the organization's culture and contribute to its growth would be impacted by the prevalence of virtual contacts (Kyeremateng, 2021).

7. Staffing and Performance Management in The Era of Covid -19

Recruiting and retaining workers who are knowledgeable about their field and enthusiastic about contributing to a company's growth is referred to as "staffing." The COVID-19 virus had a significant impact on it, altering how it functions in commercial settings (Aday, 2020). The consequences of COVID-19 on the economy were, for the most part, asymmetrical. During the worst of the outbreak, revenues in some different industries plummeted, which caused several businesses to be forced to cease operations temporarily. However, some industries saw a rise in income. Consequently, the impact that COVID-19 will have on staff will be quite variable depending on the particulars of each business (Hart & Halden, 2020).

Institutions already experiencing money difficulties due to the pandemic have implemented cutting jobs by freezing or lowering all recruitment efforts, or they have set off staff to reduce expenditures and keep the firm afloat (Aday, 2020). This has resulted in fewer jobs being available for people. Even though the COVID-19 outbreak caused millions of individuals to lose their jobs, it has been seen that employment levels have increased in numerous parts of the United States when companies have resumed normal operations. This is most likely due to the return of employees who had been put on lockdown during the infectious disease outbreak. On the other hand, individuals who have been unemployed for a long time have a far lower likelihood of getting recruited again (Hart & Halden, 2020).

Through areas of a disaster such as COVID-19, it may be essential for businesses to lay off employees. For those who work in Human Resource Management (HRM) one of the most challenging aspects is ensuring that managers and employees get the correct information when they go through this process (Barhate et al., 2022). However, it may be difficult to do in these uncertain circumstances. No one in the world has any clue when this pandemic will end, nor do they know if its consequences on companies will be temporary or permanent. On the other hand, companies that developed during the pandemic have run into other sorts of labour challenges (Barhate et al., 2022). Many individuals have decided to work via transitory firms, as a freelance, or in the "gig economy" as a consequence of the instability brought on by COVID-19. Even though these businesses have significantly increased their recruitment efforts, they still need more available labour. In point of fact, how will new staff members be recruited if everyone is scared about becoming sick? How are employees selected if there is no opportunity for direct interaction between the candidate and the employer due to safety concerns?

As a consequence, many businesses have begun using online tools for recruitment and selection procedures. This may provide a new challenge for those who work in Human Resource Management (HRM) and those looking for work (Barhate et al., 2022). The ability to effectively use current information and communication technologies is innate in some individuals. Moreover, Human Resource Management (HRM) specialists were prepared for such a dramatic change (Barhate et al., 2022). Virtual selection procedures may harm productivity and staff retention since they hinder both the capacity of candidates and employers to assess individual fit.

Additionally, the ephemeral nature of flexible work agreements contributed to the difficulties in keeping employees, making the problem even more difficult to solve. Because of this pandemic, several industry professionals suggest that one of the most significant challenges for firms is retaining talented personnel. It is important to highlight that any damage done to working relationships during trying times characterized by sudden and unexpected changes may drastically bring down employee morale and increase employee turnover. Research also indicates that in the post-COVID-19 era, it may be challenging for business owners to retain and employ talented employees because those workers are looking for work in businesses less influenced by the epidemic (Barhate et al., 2022). This may make it more difficult for companies to retain and recruit workers. Participation from workers and a sense of community inside a business are essential to its success and have the potential to reduce expensive employee turnover in the years to come. This is particularly relevant for the expanding population working from home (Barhate et al., 2022).

The performance management system of a firm should constantly identify, measure, and improve individual and team performance. Additionally, the system should connect the development of employees and teams with the organization's long-term strategic goals. It is of the utmost importance to determine whether or not the employees' efforts are per the firm's long-term goals (Barhate et al., 2022). Despite this, it is required that workers perform at a high level to assist the company in weathering the storm of COVID-19. On the other hand, it would

seem that the COVID-19 epidemic has also impacted performance management in commercial enterprises. According to the claims of some authors, the intricacy and unpredictability of the COVID-19 pandemic have resulted in a significant decline in, if not outright abandonment of, performance evaluation among most businesses (Hai & Van, 2021).

This involves assessing employees' performance and suspending remuneration dependent on their performance (Hai & Van, 2021). During this time of crisis, it may be challenging to assess employees' productivity levels due to the changing dynamics of the workplace.

The COVID-19 outbreak has several repercussions that might impact workers' productivity (Hai & Van, 2021). According to the findings of a study that focused primarily on workers who work from home as a result of COVID-19, significant predictors of workers' performance include workplace isolation, communication gaps, family misdirection, heavy workloads, and work-related stress factors (role conflicts, role ambiguity, professional life, and job-control). In addition, supervisors need to be conversant with the details of managing a remote team to ensure that remote employees' productivity is maximized (Hai & Van, 2021).

Some studies argue that supervisors may not recognize remote work because they might start believing it affects workers' performance. This could lead to the use of micro-managing, which employees could construe as a lack of trust forward within them, which could lead to conflict between the two parties. Other researchers argued that managers might not accept tasks because they may believe it does not affect employees' performance (Hai & Van, 2021).

In this moment of a public health crisis, enterprises need to keep up with and even strengthen the performance management procedures they have in place. They have to share essential information connected to the company's overall strategic direction with their workers to obtain useful business data and give feedback to them (Hai & Van, 2021). This is done in order to ensure that the company is moving in the right way. These firms will have an easier time keeping their expertise and avoiding legal problems due to this. Regularly reviewing staff performance fosters education and collaboration from those individuals, a process that may aid firms in recovering lost clients. This may be accomplished by assessing the achievements of workers (Kyeremateng, 2021).

According to the results of the study, when taking into consideration the correlation between the tasks of Human Resource Management (HRM), compensation may have a significant impact on the performance of employees during the COVID-19 period. This conclusion was reached after taking into account the connection between the duties. Because of this, the authors suggested that companies should be more worried about the total income, both financial and non-financial, of their employees, as well as the equitable of that pay, in order to keep their performance at a high level and even improve it during times of economic uncertainty. The capacity of the organization to acquire money may be the most challenging barrier to overcome as this pandemic continues (Hai & Van, 2021).

8. Opportunities, Future Organizational Directions, and Insights into Resource Management (HRM) Interventions

COVID-19 has posed considerable new challenges for managers and Human Resource Management (HRM) experts, but it has also opened up potential new opportunities. Crises may deliver businesses with unforeseen openings. COVID-19 has forced enterprises to think outside the box and has sparked conversations about the direction of the workforce (Mendy, 2021). This has hastened the interruption of Human Resource Management (HRM) and the actualization of future-focused scenarios. Additionally, it has led organizations to re-evaluate their Human Resource Management (HRM) strategies and go beyond traditional Human Resource Management (HRM) models, seeing innovative I.T. as essential to their continued success. As a result, several countries have passed new legislation to help firms deal with this disruption.

For instance, to facilitate the introduction of remote work in businesses, Germany has implemented new laws to enable the option of virtual meetings in two domains. So, working from home is rapidly becoming the norm in business. Others have argued that we need to find out how many businesses that have started using remote workers will keep doing so after COVID-19 because of how recently it was established (Kyeremateng, 2021). This is a novel approach to office management, so they are probably testing its usefulness before settling on a single strategy. Since they have not seen the results, they cannot predict how it will affect employee productivity. Flexibility in scheduling, reduced commute times, more employee agency, and exposure to cutting-edge technologies are some benefits that remote workers enjoy. It also helps companies save profit by creating better use of essential resources like office buildings. Businesses that do not need direct human interaction are on the rise in certain countries, such as Korea. This includes the telecommunications industry, remote help solutions, and online education (Mendy, 2021).

COVID-19 provides chances for businesses to increase the independence of their workers, improve their digital abilities, and extend their viewpoint on the growth of their competencies. Due to widespread knowledge, new knowledge has emerged as a potential strategic spouse for enterprises (Kyeremateng, 2021). It has made it possible to decrease the time separating workers and their employers while maintaining the employees' safety. Workplace health and safety administration has also benefited from the new technology, which has helped support it. It may be helpful for Human Resource Management (HRM) practitioners to establish the appropriate Human Resource Management (HRM) actions and future activities if they first identify the opportunities produced by COVID-19 (Mendy, 2021).

The ubiquitous effects of this epidemic, which do not appear to end any time soon, are currently being felt by organizations located all over the globe. In this situation, organizations need to generate inventive answers to successfully absorb and confront disturbances that pose a danger to their continued existence. Management and Human Resource Management (HRM) practitioners need to investigate efficient methods of incorporating information systems into HRM and adapting it to the specifics of their firm (Donthu et al., 2020). Employers need to provide their workers with the opportunity to work from home as well as the freedom to pick

when and where they complete their job. Managers should provide continuous feedback to promote increased learning and collaboration among staff members (Kyeremateng, 2021). In addition to this, they should design wellness programs to preserve the workers' mental health. The many potential configurations of work schedules that may be tailored to the needs of the present situation should be brought up in conversations between managers and the workers under their supervision. Through the company's intranet, a digital organizational culture handbook must be made accessible to workers who are working remotely in the business (Donthu et al., 2020).

9. Overcoming the Challenges of Covid- 19

This research shows that change is constant in businesses. In the field of Human Resource Management (HRM), Covid-19 has wrought revolutionary changes. Without effective management, these transitions may lead to chaos and decreased output. As a result, Human Resource Management (HRM) must be prepared to deal with new issues as they arise (Aday, 2020). In light of the above, the following suggestions were made to deal with the difficulties provided by the coronavirus since change is inevitable, Human Resource (HR) managers should always be flexible. The corporate sector is notoriously volatile, making it more important for Human Resource (HR) professionals to be updated on future developments and difficulties. This is because the organization's success depends on its contributions, and any lack might undermine those efforts (Aday, 2020), Human Resource (HR) experts should be able to orient people (through a programmed orientation) to the changes, their consequences, and the implications for the operations of the business, its employees, and other stakeholders with relative ease. It is impossible to overstate a company's value with a continuous learning culture. Stakeholders may better prepare for a crisis that might devastate business operations if they clearly understand what is expected of them and the potential repercussions of failing to meet those expectations (Habes 2020; Habes et al. 2023; Ziani et al. 2021). This is especially true concerning the company's fundamental Human Resource (HR) activities. It is recommended that risk management, finance, and I.T. collaborate on the development of such plans (Aday, 2020), Third, Human Resource (HR) workers must introduce new processes and policies to make the new opportunities more accessible.

Careful interactions with workers at all levels should be undertaken, emphasizing interpersonal connection rather than control, standard, and hierarchy. This may be accomplished by placing a high confidence level in the knowledgeable staff and providing them with consistent encouragement and assistance (Aday, 2020), The H.R. department should promote leadership styles that are efficient and successful but also adaptable enough to deal with unexpected shifts in the organization's personnel, operations, structure, and external environment. As mentioned above, "Human Resource Management (HRM) flexibility" refers to how well and quickly policies and procedures may adapt to changing conditions (Aday, 2020), Fifth, it is crucial to stress the necessity of learning how to handle information effectively so that you can separate fact from fiction or real news from fraudulent or discredited reports. Finding reliable sources of information can help develop plans to keep the company afloat regardless of the obstacles it faces (Aday, 2020).

8. FINDING AND DISSCUSSIONS

1. Discussion

Succession planning strategies should be developed by Human Resource Management (HRM). As a result of succession planning, more qualified employees will be ready to take on leadership positions and the responsibilities that come with them (Kyeremateng, 2021). The ability of an organization to grow and adapt to meet future demands is bolstered by succession planning, which in turn aids in the cultivation of talent among existing staff. For businesses, succession planning is a tool for talent management and retention. In the retail industry, where the number of instances of Covid-19 is rising at an alarming rate, it is especially important to have a solid succession plan to assist in advancing the careers of current workers and guarantee a smooth transition should any key personnel leave. According to studies, a well-thought-out succession plan increases a company's chances of success and keeps its leaders and followers around for the long haul (Ichsan et al., 2020). Many retail businesses, especially small and medium retailers, are suffering financial issues; therefore, Human Resource Management (HRM) should prepare for layoffs with the highest reason in addition to preparing for succession, depending on the requirement. In the case of Covid-19, small and medium-sized stores are experiencing cash flow problems and are planning to reduce their workforce (Kyeremateng, 2021). According to a poll by the research, small stores plan to lay off 30% of their personnel, medium stores want to cut 12% of their employees, and major stores plan to slash 5% of their workforce. Human Resource Management (HRM) is responsible for carrying out its duties fairly and impartially, protecting the shops' reputations at all times, whether via succession planning for replacing staff or layoffs due to downsizing (Ichsan et al., 2020).

Now no actual immunization can be obtained in any part of the world, making the pandemic situation more dangerous daily. The Human Resource (HR) department may educate staff on proper hygiene practices to lessen the likelihood of the dreaded COVID-19 virus being disseminated before the vaccine is made accessible (Zhu, 2020). The leadership of H.R. needs to maintain a level of composure while also seizing the initiative to respond to any given circumstance in a way that is direct, assertive, and communicates with employees at all levels of the organization. Only in this way can the well-being of everyone involved be ensured (Zhu, 2020). Workers directly responsible for customer service are crucial for the survival of any retail firm. All retail companies must provide comprehensive training to their first-line employees on subjects such as the appropriate use of sanitizers, the significance of wearing gloves when working with food products, and the necessity of keeping clean work areas (Zhu, 2020). Since front-line laborers are in nearer contact with clients than higher management, all retail companies must provide this training. Because only properly educated staff can give customers service that is to their satisfaction, it is essential to place a strong focus on training front-line sales workers about hygiene and other relevant themes (Zhu, 2020)

Regarding Covid-19, Human Resource Management (HRM) is tasked with various obligations, including updating the group's health policy. It is the responsibility of employees to convince senior management to allow for the implementation of health rules in retail outlets. These policies should safeguard employees' health and give them confidence in their career prospects.

Covid-19 is the name of a new policy that Walmart, the biggest retailer in the world, put into effect in March 2020 to safeguard better the wellness of its workforce (Ahmed et al., 2020). The primary element of the policy is that employees are no longer obligated to go to work even if they are experiencing symptoms of illness. Any Walmart employee placed into isolation by police departments or the firm itself will receive two weeks' pay and have their absenteeism excused. This policy applies whether the order comes from Walmart or law enforcement. Suppose an employee is unable to come back to work owing to a confirmed case of a virus. In that case, the employee may be entitled to up to 26 additional weeks of pay replacement, regardless of whether or not the individual works full- or part-time hours. The organization's mission is to ensure that the working environment is one in which every employee can consistently report feeling safe and secure (Ahmed et al., 2020). Managing flexible working arrangements, employee connectivity to increase awareness, addressing employee complaints on workplace rules, implementing precautionary measures, and evaluating current welfare policies are all tasks that Human Resource Management (HRM) should undertake during the pandemic outbreak of Covid-19 (Ahmed et al., 2020). Therefore, Human Resource Management (HRM) should start organizing awareness programs to plan and train on how to protect against the spread of the virus. The Human Resource Management (HRM) should sincerely ease the tension and anxiety experienced by employees so that the workers may regain their sense of self-assurance (Ahmed et al., 2020).

2. Conclusion

When assessing the significance of the contribution made by this work, it is essential to bear in mind a few limitations. Our research consists of a complete literature review to elucidate a certain topic. Because of this, it is possible that we selected the literature that we studied based on our personal preferences. The databases we have used should have the papers mentioned most often. Given the determination of this study and the fact that it is instructive, doing a comprehensive evaluation of the relevant previous research is optional. Second, the COVID-19 virus had not been eradicated when this report was published. As a direct consequence, it is hard to identify with any level of precision the potential dangers and opportunities that may crop up in the foreseeable future. The best approach for future research to identify such roadblocks and opportunities is longitudinal analysis. Because of the epidemic, everyone is quaking in their boots about the coming years. Covid-19. When lockdown and isolation procedures are implemented, it is detrimental to the economy on a global scale, particularly to retail companies. In order to weather the present economic storm, retailers more than ever need the assistance of their employees. However, Human Resource Management (HRM) must participate to get this assistance in any meaningful sense. Because businesses rely on Human Resource Management (HRM) to provide the most current information on organization and employment, it is challenging for Human Resource Management (HRM) to accomplish their work during times of crisis. The findings of this research indicate that Human Resource Management (HRM) may be able to meet these obstacles by introducing incentive programs at all tiers of retail businesses in order to motivate employees, attempting to direct all employees of retail companies to adhere to wellness guidelines, and assisting employees in overcoming their uncertainty.

9. CONTRIBUTION AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

In the business world, problems will inevitably arise at some point. No one could have predicted a crisis on the level of COVID-19, which has precipitated the disruption of conventional Human Resource Management (HRM) practices and posed major challenges to managers and Human Resource Management (HRM) professionals who lacked the necessary knowledge, skills, and assets to cope with the complexity and novelty of the pandemic (Kniffin et al., 2021). No one could have anticipated a crisis on the scale of COVID-19, which has heralded the disruption of conventional Human resource management practices and posed significant challenges to management teams and Human Resource Management (HRM) practitioners. In addition to these challenges, COVID-19 has also given opportunities that companies will have to be aware of to concentrate their Human Resource Management (HRM) efforts in the most productive manner moving ahead. This research is a review of the literature. As such, it provides managers and HRM professionals with a comprehensive overview of the most significant challenges and possible advantages of COVID-19. The predictions presented in this article for the development of humanity's resource management should assist them in developing a Human Resource (HR) strategy that is suited specifically for their particular company and employees (Kniffin et al., 2021).

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